

Sustaining Academic Excellence In An Unsecured Learning Atmosphere In Nigeria: Challenges And Way Forward

Ayaraekpe, Simeon Uduakobong

**Department of Educational Management
Faculty of Education
University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria
uayarekpe@gmail.com**

ABSTRACT

This paper examined sustaining academic excellence in an unsecured learning atmosphere. It also x-rayed the concepts; academic excellence, learning atmosphere and unsecured learning atmosphere. It went further to discuss the causes of unsecured learning atmosphere, nexus between academic excellence and secured learning atmosphere, challenges associated with sustaining academic excellence in an unsecured learning atmosphere and the way forward in addressing the challenges. In view of the content of the paper, the writer is of the opinion that, unsecured learning atmosphere disrupts effective teaching and learning process, thereby hindering sustained academic excellence. Thus, it was concluded that, a secured learning atmosphere is fundamental to the attainment of academic excellence. Based, on the conclusion, it was suggested among others that, school administrators of impeccable character with intellectual prowess and imagination should be hired to ensure effective supervision of school programmes and activities. Also, administrator in schools should work with outstretched arms to always communicate effectively to teachers and other relevant stakeholders in education. They should communicate and collaborates with subordinates to achieve school goals and make progress towards sustained academic excellence.

Keywords: Sustaining, Academic Excellence, Unsecured Learning Atmosphere

INTRODUCTION

In the past, governments of industrialized countries across the world have promoted the value of academic excellence, broadly defined as high educational achievement, in light of its contribution to economic and technological growth, social development, and individuals' well-being. The pursuit of academic excellence has been combined with a concern for improving the achievement of all students, given the pervasive insecurity outcomes that characterize many schools. The importance of sustaining academic excellence has been adequately discussed in many fora and in different literature (Nwanne-Nzewunwa, 2009; Ojukwu & Nwanma, 2015; Ojukwu, 2021). It is in realization of the importance of academics of the child that the government of the Federal Republic of Nigeria in its 1999 constitution made a declaration of the right of every Nigerian child to education, irrespective of gender, tribe, religion or race. It makes sense to state that the lofty vision of education as enunciated in the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria would be realized in a serene and conducive learning atmosphere.

Lehr (2021) opined that the noble goals of academic excellence can never be achieved in a vacuum. They would be achieved in a conducive and peaceful learning atmosphere. If there is a feeling of insecurity within and outside the learning environment, both students and teachers are likely to be deterred and this may inhibit academic excellence or performance of the students. The concept of learning atmosphere or environment has been variously defined by various researchers (Miller & Cunnighan, 2021; Obi, et al. 2014). In the view of Obi et al. (2014) learning environment connotes all human and material resources available in the school, in which a learner can see, hear, touch, smell, taste, feel and respond to. Generally, school learning environment are supposed to be a safe atmosphere for learners considering several hours they spend in school.

However, the chronic insecurity issues and lethal school violence witnessed across several states in Nigeria today both at the North and the South poses a threat in economically depressed urban and rural centers. Available statistics suggest that violence against children negatively affects enrolment at the basic level, especially as it concerns the girl child. Parents are known to have been discouraged from sending the girl-child to school out of fear for their safety. Currently, most shootings and kidnapping incidences occurred or are targeted towards school. This deteriorating security situation in Nigeria is worrisome and calls for proper management of security architecture in the schools for secured learning atmosphere.

Federal Ministry of Education (2021) reported that findings from the national survey conducted in 2014 show that there was a high prevalence of violence against school children in Nigeria. Some of the findings of the survey are highlighted below:

- i. Approximately 6 of every 10 children under the age of 18 years have experienced some form of violence in school;
- ii. About half of the children experience violence before the age of 10;
- iii. Parents and adult relatives are the most common perpetrators of physical violence on school children;
- iv. Among adults, male teachers are the most frequent perpetrators of the first incident of physical violence against school children;
- v. Less than half of all victims of physical violence tell someone about it (p.1).

The above scenario demands a drastic action in order to address the safety and security of learning environment so as to prevent threat and attack against school users, and on the other hand promote academic excellence. However, few years down the line the call has not been harken to. The attacks on education and in educational institutions have increasingly become sources of concern to all a sundry. Recent happenings point to the fact that schools are no longer safe and secure. These attacks in their various forms include but not limited to violence, kidnappings, terrorism, insurgency, gun crime, arson, vandalism, and the likes. These increased incidents of security threats destabilize the security of the school (puts at risk the safety of students, teachers, school personnel and parents) and creates an environment of insecurity and fears which impede academic activities (Patta, 2022).

For instance, in 2012, about 12 public schools across Maiduguri were burnt and about 10,000 students were forced out of school. Also in 2013, in Baga Community Secondary School in Borno state, more than 20 students and a teacher were killed by gunmen. And then, the most popular, which made global headline news, was the abduction of 200 senior secondary school girls from the school compound in Chibok, on the 16th of April 2014. Also, on the 10th of February 2018, insurgents believed to be from a faction of Boko Haram, invaded the Government Science and Technical College in Dapchi, Yobe state abducting 110 students of the school. In addition, recent event of children's death due to building collapsing, fire accidents and stampedes bring to light the need to be continually vigilant to ensure the security of students and staff in schools. The event of Kumbakoram fire tragedy which took the lives of 93 children, the Abule-Ado explosion on Sunday March 15, 2020 around Festac Town Lagos which claimed the lives of 23 students and the Plateau school building collapse on July 12, 2024 which claimed the lives of 22 students reiterates the need for a way out.

These incidents are not just peculiar to the North and West part of Nigeria alone. The South East and South-South have a share of their insecurity ordeals as well. For instance in the South-South, it is not uncommon to hear cases of abduction, sexual abuse, cultism, bullying of various forms, communal crises, interschool clashes, natural disasters, gangsterism, vandalism, robbery, theft, arson, extortion, hate crimes and demonstrations. The effects of these violence and attacks on schools are critical and are detrimental to the sustainability of academic

excellence in any nation. No country can achieve inclusive and equitable quality education if learning atmosphere is unsecured (Patta, 2022).

Consequently, it is against this background that this study sought to look at how academic excellence can be sustained despite the unsecured nature of learning atmosphere of schools in Nigeria. In this regard, the paper reviewed concepts like; academic excellence, learning atmosphere and unsecured learning atmosphere. Also, it highlighted the causes of unsecured learning atmosphere, nexus between academic excellence and secured learning environment, challenges associated with sustaining academic excellence in an unsecured learning atmosphere and the way forward in addressing the challenges.

Conceptual Clarifications

Academic Excellence

Academic excellence refers to the achievement of exceptional academic performance, characterized by high-quality learning outcomes, depth and breadth of knowledge, critical thinking and analytical skills, effective communication and problem-solving abilities, originality and creativity in research and scholarship (Olawale, 2022). It is defined as a person's demonstrated ability to perform, accomplish, and excel in academic activities. Academic excellence is not limited to achieving good grades only, but academic excellence is characterized by its ability to achieve high grades and the ability to achieve unique performance among peers. However, Ojukwu and Onuoha (2016) opined that academic excellence is more than just making good grades. It is the maximum development of your intellectual capacities and skills in service to humanity.

Learning Atmosphere

A learning atmosphere is a physical space, safe and stimulating, with good architectural facilities, designed for diverse teaching and learning programs, pedagogies and technologies, which follow a well-planned curriculum, aligned with content standards and uses instructional strategies that suit the needs of teachers and students. Zihira (2015) defined learning atmosphere or environment as a platform which allows for a free exchange of ideas. As defined by Posner (2019) and De-Lisi (2021), learning atmosphere describes the overall climate of a classroom or school. This learning atmosphere or environment is created by the interplay of the physical dimensions of a classroom with the interpersonal interactions between students and teachers. As such, a learning atmosphere can have a strong influence on the teaching and learning that occurs within it.

Learning atmosphere refers to the diverse physical locations, contexts and culture in which students learn; and learning is what a teacher is able to package for the students from the environment. Learning takes place in varied settings like outside-of school, locations and outdoor environment. This explains why the term learning atmosphere or environment is often used and preferred to be an alternative to classroom, which has limited and traditional connotations. Structural learning atmosphere includes classroom, offices, hostel, libraries, toilets, business centres, laboratories, studios, workshops, cafes, sports and recreational outfits. Other physical learning atmosphere are the school field, garden, layout and many more (Anyago, 2022).

Learning atmosphere also encompasses the organizational climate of a school or classroom which is otherwise called social environment. This consists of how individuals interact with, and treat one another, ways educational setting is organized by the teacher to facilitate learning, such as conducting classes in relevant natural ecosystem, grouping desks in specific ways, decorating the classroom with learning materials, audio, visual and digital technologies etc. It is the whole range of components and activities within which learning occurs (Anyago, 2022).

Unsecured Learning Atmosphere

Unsecured learning atmosphere or environment is defined as a space that is not safe for teaching and learning activities to take place. It is a learning atmosphere that is prone to threat or that is vulnerable. Redding (2016) opined that any learning atmosphere is space that jeopardize the safety of students, staff and the school property. It can further be explained as any environment that undermine the security of any school users. Peterson and Skaba (2021) posited that unsecured learning atmosphere is posed with threats of human and non-human elements to destroy the vital interest of the school. This is to say that learning atmosphere threats cover

all aspects of malicious intention, action or occurrence geared towards making the learning environment or school vulnerable and exposed to security risk.

Causes of Unsecured Learning Atmosphere

The state of insecurity in Nigeria could be attributed to security lapses on the part of security agents and members of the public (Otite, 2022). Abubakar as cited in Is'haq et al (2019) pinpointed that, failure of government to provide or manage the basic human needs of their citizens, ethnic disagreements, and national resource contentions as some of the factors responsible for insecurity in schools. Udoh (2015) is of the view that insecurity witnessed around learning premises or schools is caused by porous borders, illegal arms importation, proliferation of illegal arms, ethnicity, emergence of ethnic militia groups, corruption, marginalization, poor leadership, religious fanaticism/extremism, and unemployment.

In the same vein, Olawale (2022) pinpoints that unemployment, imbalanced development, corruption, weak judicial system, and porous coastal borders as causes of insecurity in Nigeria schools. Nadabo as cited in Is'haq et al (2019) sees bad leadership, corruption, and illiteracy among other factors breeding unsafe learning atmosphere in Nigeria. The scholar also pointed to politics of bitterness in which ascendance to political power is seen as a do-or-die business. This invariably leads to political thuggery and insecurity.

In addition, King (2016) states the causes of insecurity around school environment in Nigeria to include a combination of the following factors: lack of institutional capacity, lack of basic necessities, pervasive material inequalities and unfairness, ethno-religious conflicts, weak security system, loss of socio-cultural and communal value system, porous borders, rural/urban drift, anti-social and irresponsible companies, unemployment, and poverty. There is no doubt that the above mentioned factors have affected school activities. However, Patta (2022) notes that if these causes of unsecured learning environment is properly managed, it will prompt academic excellence.

Nexus between Academic Excellence and Secured Learning Environment

Dambazau as cited in Is'haq et al (2019) quoting Act 26 of 1948 on the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, sees academic excellence as not only a public good, it is also a human right that is essential for the exercise of all other human rights, especially in promoting individual freedom and empowerment. Zukang cited in Dambazau (2021) links the relationship between lack of academic excellence to poverty, poor health conditions, diminishing opportunities to social and economic advancement which often leads to criminality. Academic excellence is also essential in the military and para-military organizations which include the police that is saddled with the security of the nation. Dambazau (2021) stresses that academic excellence is used more as a strategic tool for advancement of technology needed for nation's economic and socio-cultural development. In the military, it helps the armed forces to appraise situations; to estimate the battlefield; to examine the courses of action; to interpret the environment; to project future warfare and design the battlefield; and requirement to analyze security threats.

Dike as cited in Is'haq et al (2019) submits that the socio-political and economic development of a nation and or her health are in many ways determined by the quality and level of educational attainment (academic excellence) of the population. He, however, laments that the state of education in Nigeria cannot produce the critical and creative minds Nigeria needs to guide and manage democratic system and survive as a viable nation. Lack of academic excellence among populace in Nigeria would contribute to many social ills, including crime, prostitution, and the breakdown of law and order if not checked. Dike suggested that education in Nigeria should be treated as a public-health issue in order to necessitate security at all area, thus:

without treating education as a public-health issue that requires serious attention, the youths will continue to receive inferior education; they will continue to suffer mass unemployment and armed bandits will continue to rise; the society will continue to have illiterates and mediocres as political leaders; the society will continue to have political parties without ideology, and Nigeria will continue to fall behind economically, socially and politically (p.21).

From the foregoing, it is neither exaggeration nor understatement to say that the higher a nation attains academic excellence, the stronger the nation's security of lives and property, school learning atmosphere inclusive. Hence, sustaining academic excellence should be taken seriously as it will help to deal with the issue of unsafe learning atmosphere.

Challenges Associated with Sustaining Academic Excellence in an Unsecured Learning Atmosphere

It is quite unfortunate that sustaining academic excellence in the Nigerian education system appears to have witnessed numerous controversies due to the way and manner such changes are initiated, which have at one point or the other posed serious challenges in their management and institutionalization. School, in their role as institution or atmosphere of learning, are known for their functions which made some researchers to identify more challenges that plague the management of security in the schools. Amanda as cited in Anya, et al (2019) lists the challenges to include organizational culture, perceptions of stakeholders, lack of holistic approach, absence of follow-up, and absence of support.

Also Osagiede and Idiaqhe (2019) identify some challenges and tagged them to be Nigerian based. According to them, they include: poor functional differentiation, reform goals that do not match reality, lack of progressive administration tradition, politics weak political will, lack of public understanding and support and poor commitment of the implementers. However, Anya, et al (2019:174) highlight the following as hitches that make sustaining academic excellence in a learning atmosphere that is not secured:

- i. **Inadequate Monitoring and Supervision of Activities:** So many schools lacks proper monitoring and supervision of activities, such as ensuring effective teaching and proper security system. Anekwe and Abe (2019) subscribe that monitoring and supervision improve what happens or goes on within the school system. Ideally, there should be periodic monitoring and supervision to ensure that standards are conformed and to appraise the implementation and management process.
- ii. **Poor Communication:** Poor communication hinders effective learning atmosphere or school management, more so in the management of security. The entirety of the stakeholders – the students, teachers, parents, and staff need to be well informed on the importance of academic excellence and security in the school and the society at large. All these could be realized through sensitization, which can be done through discussions, memos, presentations, trainings and reports.
- iii. **Politicization of Academic Excellence and Security:** The information about academic excellence and security remains ambiguous. There is so much noise being made about how well it is being implemented by the government without follow-up actions. Stakeholders in education should match words with action by doing a follow to ensure government implement policies that will promote academic excellence and provide security for school activities.
- iv. **Environmental Challenge:** This for Kirkland and Sutch (2009) encompasses insufficient access to resources, lack of time, and lack of training. Innovations in Nigerian education system have always been characterized by putting the cart before the horse for instance, the Universal Basic Education programme which was launched before the establishment of infrastructures needed for its implementation (Achuonye, 2008). In some areas, where the machines are available, the infrastructure and specialized teachers may not be available. The same goes for the 6-3-3-4 system of education of old, whereby the items for technical education were sent to schools where they wasted due to lack of power supply to affect their use.
In the present day, the schools are overloaded with subjects, all to enjoy enough coverage within the forty (40) or less lesson periods in a week. In the end, some subjects do not get more than two periods a week and sometimes just one period a week. Maduagwu and Nwogu (2006) posit that, principals should take cognizance of time as a precious resource in the school, allot it appropriately to school activities, in order to achieve effective teaching and learning, otherwise the principals will continue to have loopholes in their propensity to attain academic excellence and predetermined educational goals and objectives.
- v. **Cost of Learning and Security Facilities:** This has to do with the inability of schools to procure learning and security facilities due to their cost or how expensive they are.

- vi. Lack of Collaboration between the School and the Community: The saying that ‘charity begins at home’ is typical of the management of academic programmes and security in schools. If the parents and guardians do not contribute positively by modelling their homes and their environment for peaceful co-existence, all that the school does may not bear good fruits.
- vii. Incompetence of School Staff: Teachers lack the expertise in security and in some cases are compelled to teach or carry out their responsibilities without being mindful of their environment.

Way Forward

Creating an atmosphere conducive for sustaining academic excellence is one of the most important things a teacher or school authority can do. Learning atmosphere is one of the most important factors affecting student learning and academic excellence. This is an indication that it is very important to provide learners with a healthy, safe and inviting learning atmosphere where they are protected from physical and emotional harm. This is central to the mission of all schools and it should be so pursued in order to sustain academic excellence (United Nation, 2016). Consequently, school personnel should realize that healthy and safe school learning atmosphere are not just places with advanced security procedures. The focus should be making the school environment a place that will help students develop assets that will allow them to succeed even in difficult circumstances.

A secured learning atmosphere should focus on academic achievement, maintaining high standards, fostering positive relationships between staff and students and encouraging parental and community involvement (UNICEF, 2022). In order to create a safe and healthy or conducive learning atmosphere for sustaining academic excellence, efforts should be made to create a school climate that has zero tolerance for hazards and various other anti-social behaviour. In other words, a positive school atmosphere will exist when all students feel comfortable, wanted, valued, accepted and secured in an environment where they can interact with caring people whom they can trust. In view of the above, government, NGOs, communities and administrators should bear in mind that the best learning atmosphere is one that has high challenge but low stress and minimal sources of fear or hazards.

Furthermore, school administrators by virtue of their position in schools, they are chief security officers. In order to play their role in sustaining academic excellence in schools to reasonable extent in any security situation, the following can be considered:

- **Adopt of innovations and technology:** Administrators can consider and plan to adopt innovations and technology. For example, to apply on-line learning to education. On-line learning itself is a tool. It is its rightful application will promote and improve students’ learning outcomes, thereby sustaining academic excellence (Oluwuo, 2021).
- **Promotion of positive school climate:** Administrator can create successful environment that promotes internal cohesion and freedom of action as well as stimulation of ideas. Positive school climate where cross fertilization of ideas is rife remain key to the sustaining academic excellence, because school environment replete with rancor and leg pulling is not a fertile environment for academic excellence and security to be nurtured and developed. Collaboration and synergy are required. The stakeholders in education like the administrators, teachers, students, parents, government as well as the local community should be allowed to contribute their quota in the education of the children. Also, the environment should be congenial for them to contribute in the security architecture of schools (Oluwuo, 2021)
- **Incessant training and awareness on security issue:** Students and staff must trained and be well-informed about security issues in the immediate community and society at large. School administrators should always brief staff and address students on the assembly ground on daily basis, the subject matter should not base on academic issue alone (Ololobou, 2021). It is necessary to provide them with current news on security. Such news must be authentic and not rumor. The manner of presentation should not create fear in staff and students. If staff and students are not educated about what is happening by their school administrators, another person might break the news in an unpleasant manner. This may cause pandemonium in school and its effect could be consequential (Okon, et al. 2019).

- **Adequate fencing of school premises:** Schools have to be fenced to safeguard indiscriminate entry and exit. The school administrators whose schools do not have fence can sensitize parents, old students, philanthropists and government on the necessity of fence. A school that is without fence is prone to security threat. Hoodlums can easily penetrate into such school without the knowledge of security men (Aguwa, 2019).
- **Secure entrance and exit and use of metal detector and other security gadgets:** It is not sufficient to have a fence that is as tall as prison yard fence but with secure entrance and exit. The gate at the entrance should be functional and strong. The security men too have be up to the task. Corrupt men should not be engaged as security men. For the fact that somebody is an ex-soldier does not qualify him for security job, his integrity and track records matter a lot. School administrator should also acquire metal detector to discover harmful object like guns, arrows, cutlasses and other metal objective. Cases of shootings in the schools at Mexico and other states in United State of America where school children were murdered can be forestalled (Chukwudi, 2019).
Also, a study from Heon-Young (2021) indicated that Japan and United States are implementing Crime Prevention through security gadgets like CCTV camera, explosive detectors, turnstiles, boom barriers, web security cameras, blind spots cameras, doorbell ringers, smart deadbolt, siren padlock, motion sensor smart lights, barking dog alarm, pressure doormat alarm, GPS trackers and many more. In Malaysia, the number of security gadgets users is high in the private and government owned schools because it was observed that security gadgets installation in schools help to secure their premises and places, making them feel safe and reduce the rate of crime for academic activities to take place (Yahya & Aziz, 2019).
- **Strict regulation of visitors in school premises and effective use of visitor's book:** There is need for regulation and control of visitors and the time of visit during the session. Though a few school observe visiting hours during the session, it has to be intensified. Parents should be educated on the need for such regulation. If they know that this is done in the interest of their wards (for safety and effective learning), they will comply. The use of visitors' book is essential to monitor personalities that visit the school. If it is possible, the visitors should be requested to provide evidence of identification. This will send a signal to people that have ulterior motives to stay clear from the school premises (Oladipo et al., 2021).
- **Regular inspection of school premises:** Regular inspection of school premises to uncover strange objects is essential. Security men and assigned staff have to move round the school premises once or twice in a day to find out if crime activities or strange objects will be discovered. If strange objects or unusual signs are observed, they should be reported as soon as possible to the concerned authority (Xaba, 2019).
- **Safety measures in school plant construction and classroom designs:** As part of safety measures, contractors who handle construction of school buildings and classrooms should be instructed to incorporate safety precautions. For instance, every classroom is expected to have entrance and exit doors. This is very important to forestall stampede in case of emergency. The chairs in the class rooms have to be spacious to facilitate easy movement (Mohammed, et al. 2019). In addition, car park in the school should be constructed not too close to school buildings. If it is possible, car parks should be closed to the school gates. This will prevent driving towards the school buildings and suicide bombers' attempt to hit school buildings. In fact, barrier that can easily prevent vehicle movement towards school building could be mounted (UNICEF, 2022).
- **Crisis preparedness:** Though it is a general slogan that prevention is better than cure, in an extreme case there is need to take step to cure. If one does not have what it takes to cure in such situation, it can be disastrous. There are safety risks that extend above and beyond the school community. For this reason, school administrators need to device measure whereby himself, teachers, students and other stakeholders are knowledgeable about what should happen in an emergency. Therefore, school administrators have to liaise with departments and agencies like National Emergency Agency (NEMA),

Police, Civil Defense, and other security agencies that can provide training that helps school to prepare to deal with terror alert and extreme acts of violence.

In addition, Nwadiani as cited in Obiechina, Abraham and Nwogu (2018) advocated the introduction of School Environmental Eesign (SED) for sustaining academic excellence in an unsecured learning atmosphere which according to him is related to school mapping. He further stated that School Environmental Design (SED) if made to work can help prevent security challenges and health hazards through the following:

- a. **Natural surveillance:** This is the act of arranging physical facilities and features in schools to ensure and maximize visibility.
- b. **Natural access control:** This involves all conscious activities to control who comes into the school and where and how far they can go to. They have to be guided with security in mind. In short you work with the assumption that every visitor is a potential threat. They should be checked thoroughly but with dignity.
- c. **Territorial reinforcement:** By this approach, the school land and boundaries are properly demarcated by fencing, landscaping and signs flavoured with aesthetic like flower and tree planting.
- d. **Continuous maintenance of school infrasturcture:** A workable culture of maintenance should be put in place, such that all school architecture and other facilities function maximally (p. 27-28).

CONCLUSION

The importance of learning atmosphere to the sustenance of academic excellence cannot be over-emphasized. Unsecured learning atmosphere disrupts effective teaching and learning and also important school activities which invariably affects teachers' level of productivity. Therefore, a secured learning atmosphere is fundamental to the attainment of academic excellence.

SUGGESTIONS

The following suggested in view of the challenges associated with sustaining academic excellence in an unsecured learning atmosphere:

1. School administrators of impeccable character with intellectual prowess and imagination should be hired to ensure effective supervision of school programmes and activities.
2. Administrator in schools should work with outstretched arms to always communicate effectively to teachers and other relevant stakeholders in education. They should communicate and collaborates with subordinates to achieve school goals and make progress towards sustained academic excellence.
3. There should be annual evaluation of academic programmes in all institutions of learning rather than it politicization.
4. Government that is in charge of public educational institutions should remunerate teachers appropriately, provide infrastructure to cater for effective teaching and learning, as well as security architecture of schools.
5. School managers should not see technology, as a silver bullet, a one shot thing as more technology does not mean better learning. Technology should be used to boost and sustain academic excellence and school security. For example, in schools especially in the urban areas in Nigeria, should be provided with laptops, interactive white boards, smart phones, tablets, desktops, constant electricity supply and a lot of other.
6. Recruitment of staff in schools should be based on merit rather than ethnicity and favouritism. Teachers with sound mind should be recruited to drive academic excellence.
7. There is need for training and retraining of teaching staff to enable them have adequate theoretical foundations in teaching to enhance academic excellence.
8. Government should as a matter of urgency deploy trained, qualified and experienced security guards to all public schools to increase the ability to monitor and foil attacks of intruders or criminal agents that would breach peaceful and safe learning atmosphere of schools.
9. Government should solicit the support of private business organisations and NGOs to assist in the procurement and installation of security gadgets in the school, taking it as their corporate social

responsibility project, in order to promote safe learning atmosphere for sustained academic activities. Some of these gadgets should include: CCTV camera, alarms, metal detectors, walkie-talkies, bomb detectors, web security cameras, blind spots cameras, doorbell ringers, siren padlock, motion sensor smart lights, barking dog alarm, GPS trackers, and many others.

10. Government and school authority should not fail to always invite the community vigilante, police and her sister agencies for patrol around school premises, as this will help to scare and prevent criminal activities within and around school environment.

REFERENCES

- Achuonye, K. A. (2008). *Trends in Nigerian educational innovations*. Pearl publishers
- Aguwa, A. (2019). *Management of insecurity for effective administration of secondary schools in Abia State*. An Unpublished PhD Thesis of Abia State University, Uturu.
- Anekwe, J. U., & Abe, E. C. (2019). Innovation and change in school inspection and supervision. In J.O. Ajuonuma, J.D. Asodike, and R.O. Anyaogu (Eds.). *Issues and trends in change and innovation in Nigerian educational system*. Pearl Publishers
- Anya, E. C., Madumere-Obike, C. U., & Onyeike, V. C. (2019). Management strategies and challenges of peace and security education for quality service delivery in secondary schools in Rivers State. *African Journal of Educational Research and Development (AJERD)*, 12(1), 169-182.
- Anyaogu, R. O. (2022). Creating conducive learning environment and management: A panacea for effective learning and creativity in schools. *International Journal of Academia*, 2(1), 1-9.
- Chukwudi, J. (2019). *Safety management for quality work environment of public primary schools in Abia State*. An unpublished thesis of Abia State University, Uturu.
- Dambazau, A. (2021). *Education, security and national development: The case of Nigeria*. Paper Presented for the 61st Interdisciplinary Research Discourse, The Postgraduate School, University of Ibadan on 5th November, at the Main Hall, Conference Centre, University of Ibadan.
- Federal Ministry of Education (2021). *National policy on safety, security and violence-free schools with its implementing guidelines*. FME & EEWGN.
- Heon-Young, P. (2021). The discussion of CCTV effect for crime prevention through environmental design in Korea. *International Journal of Criminal Study*, 2(2), 17–21.
- Is'haq, A. B.; Musa, Tope Aisha; and Abdulhafiz, Z. (2019). *Education and insecurity in Nigeria*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332548880>
- King, U. (2016). *Security challenges in Nigeria and the implications for business activities and sustainable development*. <http://nsacc.org.ng/security-challenges-in-nigeria-and-the-implications-for-business-activities-and-sustainable-development/>
- Kirkland, K., & Sutch, D. (2009). *Overcoming the barriers to educational innovation: A literature review*. <https://www.nfer.ac.uk/publications/FUT61.pdf>.
- Lehr, C. A. (2021). *Positive school climate; information for education*. National Association of School Psychologists. <http://www.nasponline.org/.../school-climate-hopds>
- Maduagwu, S. N., & Nwogu, U. J. (2006). *Resource allocation and management in education*. Alphabet publishers.
- Miller, A., & Cunnighan, K. (2021). *Classroom environment*. www.education.com/.../classroom
- Mohammed, K., Alimba, C. N., Momodu, A. J., & Ika, G. M. (2019). *Boko Haram Insurgency and School Attacks in Northeastern, Nigeria*. Research Study Commissioned by UNICEF, Nigeria.
- Nwanna-Nzewunwa, O. P. (2009). *Sociology of education for certificate and diploma students*. Springfield Publishers Limited.
- Obi, T. E. C., Johnson, H. I., & Lawani .C. (2014). *The school environment and the child*. National Open University of Nigeria.
- Obiechina, F. N., Abraham, N. M., & Nwogu, U. J. (2018). Perceived impact of school environmental insecurity on teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Social & Science Education Research*, 6(4):43-48.

- Ojukwu, M. & Onuoha, T. (2016). Perception of students on causes of poor performance in chemistry in External Examinations in Umuahia North Local Government Area of Abia State. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*, 4 (1), 67 - 73.
- Ojukwu, M. O. (2021). Effect of insecurity of school environment on the academic performance of secondary school students in Imo state, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education & Literacy Studies*, 5(1), 20-28.
- Ojukwu, M., O., & Nwanna, A., C. (2015). Influence of insecurity of school environment on the behaviour of secondary school students in Isiala-Ngwa North and South Local Government Area of Abia State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education & Literacy Studies*, 3(4), 49 – 55.
- Okon, J. E., Akuegwu, B. A., & Uko, E. S. (2019). *Emerging issues in educational administration, planning and supervision*. University of Calabar Press
- Oladipo, S. A., Awoyinfa, J. O., & Adefarakan, O. S. (2021). Institutional critical factors in university personnel security. *International Journal of Innovative Business Strategies (IJIBS)*, 4(2), 219-227.
- Olawale, A. (2022). *Top 5 causes of insecurity in Nigeria*. <http://nigerianfinder.com/top-5-causes-of-insecurity-in-nigeria/>
- Ololobou, C.O. (2021). Quality assurance in primary basic education through adequate provision, distribution and utilization of instructional materials. *Nigerian Journal of curriculum studies*, 3, 227-234.
- Oluwuo, S. O. (2021). *Management of innovation education for the attainment of sustainable development goals*. A Keynote Address Presented at the Conference Organized by University of Port Harcourt Chapter of Nigerian Association for Educational Administration and Planning (NAEAP) Held at Ebitimi Banilgo Hall Abuja Unipark, University of Port Harcourt from Monday 17th to Thursday 20th May, 2021.
- Osagiede, M. A., & Idiaghe, J. E. (2019). Educational reform and innovation in teacher education in Nigeria: Way forward for quality education. *Journal of Teacher Perspective*, 3(1), 133 – 143.
- Otite, E. (2022). *State of insecurity in Nigeria: A challenge to the government*. http://nnn.com.ng/?page_id=4449
- Patta, E. (2022). *Management of security and achievement of sustainable development goal 4 in public secondary schools in Rivers State*. Unpublished Ph.D Thesis Submitted to the Department of Educational Planning, University of Port Harcourt.
- Peterson, R. L., & Skaba, R. (2021). Creating school violence. *The Clearing House*, 76, (3) 115-163.
- Posner, G. J. (2019). The extensiveness of curriculum structure: A conceptual scheme. *Review of Educational Research*, 44(4), 401–407. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543044004401>
- Redding, S. (2016). *The mega system: A Handbook for continuous improvement within a community of the school*. <http://www.center/org/survey>
- Smith, S., & De-Lisi, G. (2021). *Classroom environment*. <http://www.enotes.com/research-starters/classroomenvironment#research-starter-research-starter>
- Udoh, A. (2015). *Security and school environment*. *Journal of International Research and Education*, 7(3), 73-91.
- United Nations (2016). *Transforming our world: the 2030 agenda for sustainable development*. General Assembly Seventieth Session Agenda.
- United Nations Children’s Fund (2022). *Reimagined the future*. UNICEF
- Xaba, M. (2019). A holistic approach to safety and security at schools in South Africa. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(20), 1580-1589.
- Yahya, R. M., & Aziz, S. S. (2019). A Study on the effectiveness of Closed- Circuit Television (CCTV) Camera’s. *Advances in Environmental Biology*, 9(10), 255–260.
- Zihira, R. K. (2021). *Urban environmental hazards: A case study of flood hazards in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia*. Unpublished Ph.D Thesis, University of Nottingham.